

Application of LiDAR-based DTMs and DSMs to detect landforms created by the tree uprooting process

Janusz Godziek

Institute of Earth Sciences, Faculty of Natural Sciences
University of Silesia in Katowice
Sosnowiec, Poland
janusz.godziek@us.edu.pl

Abstract— Tree uprooting plays a significant role in shaping the microtopography in forested areas. This process leads to the formation of 1) pit-mound topography (with adjacent pit and mound forms being a result of the tree uprooting) and 2) root plates (with undecomposed root systems and soil material attached to them). The increasing availability and accuracy of LiDAR point clouds enable producing high-resolution DTMs and DSMs. Such models can be applied to detect even small forms with a diameter below 3 meters.

In the present project DTMs and DSMs were used to detect the location of 1) treethrow pit-mound pairs and 2) root plates of uprooted trees. Analysis was performed for selected 100x100 m research plots situated within the Babia Góra National Park (BgNP; Western Carpathians, Southern Poland). We used an open-source point cloud from the Polish Institute of Geodesy and Cartography (density: 20 pts/m²). All steps of the analysis were automated with the use of R programming language. Closed contour lines can be used to detect both types of forms. For pit-mound pairs detection, we tested different DTM resolutions and contour line intervals to achieve the best accuracy of the proposed contour method (CM). In the case of root plate detection, the point cloud was reduced to the points of the last return of the laser beam to maximize the chances of catching the points that actually reflect the locations of root plates and trunks. A differential model (DM) was produced by applying double classification of ground reflections with the use of a cloth simulation function algorithm (CSF). A contour line of the height of 1 m calculated from the DM was used to extract the potential locations of root plates.

The study has been supported by the Polish National Science Centre (project no 2019/35/O/ST10/00032).

I. INTRODUCTION

Tree uprooting is one of the main processes shaping the forest floor microrelief [12] (Fig. 1). This process is driven mainly by hurricane-force winds, which cause the trees to fall. Trees may be damaged in two ways, i.e. 1) by stem breakage and 2) by uprooting. The stem breakage does not have an impact on the forest floor microtopography, while during uprooting, the soil and bedrock material attached to roots is uplifted in the root system [11]. The root plates formed in this way consist of 1) undecomposed root systems and 2) soil and bedrock material. The subsequent process of the root system decomposition causes the soil and bedrock material to move down. This leads to a gradual disintegration of a root plate, which may last from several years to several decades. The disintegration process is controlled by climate, soil properties, and root plate volume [10]. Finally, a treethrow mound forms as a remnant of the root plate. In most cases, a treethrow mound has an adjacent pit, which was created during tree uprooting in the place previously occupied by the tree root system. Such neighboring convex and concave forms indicate the place, where the tree was uprooted and create the so-called pit-mound topography [8]. The entire process of pit-mound topography formation can be considered an example of hillslope biomorphodynamics, i.e. the impact of living organisms on the creation and evolution of landforms and soils [11, 13].

Currently, the availability of accurate Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) data is growing. Hence, Digital Terrain Models (DTMs) and Digital Surface Models (DSMs) can be produced with very fine, submeter resolution. This allows the application of this data to detect small microtopography forms

Figure 1. A – The process of tree uprooting and pit-mound topography formation (after [7]). B – Uprooted tree with a root plate and stem (Photo. J. Godziek 2022).

with diameters below 3 m. Therefore LiDAR data may be an excellent source of information about the landforms resulting from the tree uprooting process.

Under the present project, we investigated the application of DTMs and DSMs to detect the location of 1) pit-mound pairs and 2) root plates of uprooted trees. We made an attempt to automate the detection process with the use of R programming language. Analysis was conducted for selected 100x100 m research plots located within the Babia Góra National Park (BgNP; Western Carpathians, Southern Poland). We applied open-source point cloud data from the Polish Head Office of Geodesy and Cartography (density: 20 points/m²). We used a closed contour lines approach to extract the location of forms. This approach was previously applied to detect karst landforms [4] and surface depressions [14].

II. DETECTION METHODS AND RESULTS

A. Pit-mound topography

For pit-mound topography detection, we proposed the contour method (CM) allowing extraction of the location of individual pit-mound pairs [3] (Fig. 2). We produced DTM from LiDAR data. We tested three DTM resolutions: 0.5 m, 0.25 m, and 0.1 m. After that, we delineated contour lines and computed the length of each contour line. Three contour line intervals were tested: 0.25 m, 0.1 m, and 0.05 m. Then we filtered contour lines by selecting only those with the length within a particular interval. We checked three length intervals: 1.5 – 25 m, 2.5 – 20 m, and 3.5 – 15 m. In the next step, we converted selected contour lines into polygons. Finally, we classified these polygons into objects representing convex and

concave forms by analyzing the location of the maximum and minimum elevation within the polygon.

We prepared the validation dataset by recognizing pit and mound forms manually, „on-screen”. The recognition was based on several criteria, i.e. 1) the values of the Topographic Position Index (TPI), 2) the characteristic shape of contour lines between adjacent pits and mounds, indicating the formation of both forms as a result of a single tree uprooting. We marked 74 pit-mound pairs in two research areas.

The next step was to compare the results of the CM with the validation dataset. Out of 27 tested variants of the CM, the best one (1st) reached accuracies around 95% for pits, 90-93% for mounds, and 85-90% for pit-mound pairs. For the 1st variant, we performed additional computations. We selected adjacent pits and mounds, located at a distance below 1.5 m. This enabled the assignment of a single pit to a single mound. Then we plotted the probable locations of pit-mound pairs on the map. The entire analysis described above was automated with the R script.

B. Root plates of uprooted trees

To obtain validation data on root plates location, measurements were carried out in the area of a forest stand damaged by the windstorm in November 2004 and strictly protected since 2005 [15]. On two research plots, we measured the location of 205 root plates using a GNSS receiver with an accuracy of 0.05 m. These measurements enabled us to estimate the accuracy of the proposed detection method.

We observed that the root plates of uprooted trees are visible in the LiDAR point clouds. To maximize the chances of catching the points that actually reflect the locations of root

Fig. 2. Workflow of the pit-mound topography and root plates detection methods.

plates and trunks, we selected only the points marking the last return of the laser beam. To extract the location of root plates we performed double classification of ground reflections using the cloth simulation function (CSF) available in the lidR package [16] (Fig. 2). In the first classification we applied default parameters of the CSF algorithm and as a result we obtained DTM. In the second classification, we changed the parameters of the CSF algorithm (sloop_smooth = T, class_threshold = 3). The outcome of the computation was the DSM representing terrain surface, root plates, fallen trunks, and dense understory vegetation. Then we produced the differential model (DM) using the formula: $DM = DSM - DTM$. All computations were performed in a spatial resolution of 0.25 m.

We computed the contour lines of the DM in the interval of 0.1 m. Then we visually inspected the shape and layout of the contour lines of the root plates. We observed, that the contour line of the height of 1 m closes on the majority of root plates. We decided to use this contour line to extract the location of root plates. We converted the contour of the height of 1 m into polygons. We excluded from further analysis small polygons of the area below 0.2 m². Then we classified polygons into „root plates” and „false positives” using GNSS field measurements. The next step was to filter polygons to decrease the number of false positives. Therefore for each polygon, we calculated the following parameters: area, perimeter, the distance between the

outermost vertices of the polygon boundary, polygon compactness index [1], zonal statistics of the DM (maximum, minimum, average, range, standard deviation), and morphometric indices (circulatory ratio [6], elongation ratio [2], hypsometric integral [9], and relief ratio [13]). For morphometric indices, we used values of the DM as height and the distance between the outermost vertices of the polygon boundary as „catchment” length. Then we analyzed the distribution of values of the above-mentioned parameters on the box plots. For each parameter, we produced two box plots considering two groups of features: root plates and false positives. We performed also visual, „on-screen” analysis of the values of particular polygons. Finally, we decided to select only polygons of area greater than 1 m² and polygon compactness index smaller than 1.9 (Fig. 3).

Accurate boundaries of root plates are required to extract the volume of these forms. To delineate boundaries, we created a 1 m buffer along the selected polygons representing the contour lines of the height of 1 m. Then we reclassified the DM. We assigned the value „1” to all pixels greater or equal to 0.2 m and the value „0” to all other pixels. We polygonized such reclassified raster and removed all polygons located below 0.2 m (with value „0”). Then we performed an intersection between 1 m buffers and polygons with value „1”. Finally, we simplified and smoothed the shape of the resulting polygons.

Fig. 3. Distribution of the values of area and polygon compactness index – data for polygons extracted from the contour line of the height of 1 m. Mean value marked by a triangle.

Initial results indicate quite a high accuracy of the proposed root plate detection method for the selected area of interest. Out of all 90 finally selected polygons, 60 were marked in the field as root plates and 30 are false positives. Hence the accuracy of the proposed method can be estimated at 66%.

III. CONCLUSIONS

Both proposed methods achieved an accuracy above 60%. The methods perform well in the selected study area, however concerning the concept of the area of applicability [5] they are spatially limited. Therefore further testing on other areas and with different datasets is required. The results are strongly impacted by the quality of the point cloud data used in the study. The point cloud density of 20 pts/m² enables the recognition of microforms of diameter 1-3 m created due to the tree uprooting. Presumably point clouds of smaller densities do not enable such detection. The DTM resolution does not exert a significant impact on the detection outputs. To detect microforms, the contour line interval should be significantly smaller than the height of the forms. The methods presented in this paper may be applied to assess the scale and impact of the tree uprooting process in mid-latitudes forests and can be used in research in geomorphology, soil science, and forest ecology.

IV. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The study has been supported by the Polish National Science Centre (project no 2019/35/O/ST10/00032).

REFERENCES

- [1] Brinkhoff, T., Kriegel, H. P., Schneider, R., & Braun, A., 1995. Measuring the Complexity of Polygonal Objects. In: ACM-GIS, p. 109.
- [2] Eagleson, P.S., 1970. Dynamic Hydrology. McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York, 462.
- [3] Godziek, J., Pawlik, Ł., 2023. Indicators of wind-driven forest disturbances – pit–mound topography, its automatic detection and significance. CATENA 221, 106757. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2022.106757>
- [4] Liang, F., Du, Y., Ge, Y., Li, C., 2014. A quantitative morphometric comparison of cockpit and doline karst landforms. J. Geogr. Sci. 24, 1069–1082. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11442-0141139-6>
- [5] Meyer, H., Pebesma, E., 2021. Predicting into unknown space? Estimating the area of applicability of spatial prediction models. Methods Ecol Evol 12, 1620–1633. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13650>
- [6] Miller, V.C., 1953. Quantitative geomorphic study of drainage basin characteristics in the Clinch Mountain area, Virginia and Tennessee. Technical report (Columbia University. Department of Geology), 3.
- [7] Pawlik, Ł., 2013. The role of trees in the geomorphic system of forested hillslopes — A review. Earth-Science Reviews 126, 250–265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2013.08.007>
- [8] Pawlik, Ł., Migoń, P., Owczarek, P., Kacprzak, A., 2013. Surface processes and interactions with forest vegetation on a steep mudstone slope, Stołowe Mountains, SW Poland. CATENA 109, 203–216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2013.03.011>
- [9] Pike, R.I., Wilson, S.E., 1971. Elevation relief ratio, Hypsometric integral and geomorphic area altitude analysis. Geol. Soc. Am. Bull. 82: 1079–1084.
- [10] Šamonil, P., Antolík, L., Svoboda, M., Adam, D., 2009. Dynamics of windthrow events in a natural fir-beech forest in the Carpathian mountains. Forest Ecology and Management 257, 1148–1156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2008.11.024>
- [11] Šamonil, P., Daněk, P., Schaetzl, R.J., Vašíčková, I., Valtera, M., 2015. Soil mixing and genesis as affected by tree uprooting in three temperate forests. European Journal of Soil Science 66, 589–603. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12245>
- [12] Schaetzl, R.J., Burns, S.F., Small, T.W., Johnson, D.L., 1990. Tree Uprooting: Review of Types and Patterns of Soil Disturbance. Physical Geography 11, 277–291. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02723646.1990.10642407>
- [13] Strahler, A.N., 1964 Quantitative geomorphology of drainage basin and channel networks. In: Chow, V.T., (Ed.) Handbook of Applied Hydrology. McGraw-Hill, New York. pp 439–476.
- [14] Wu, Q., Liu, H., Wang, S., Yu, B., Beck, R., Hinkel, K., 2015. A localized contour tree method for deriving geometric and topological properties of complex surface depressions based on high-resolution topographical data. International Journal of Geographical Information Science 29, 2041–2060. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2015.1038719>
- [15] Zadrożny, P., Kružel, J., Lamorski, T., Nicia, P., Kozina, P., 2017. Changes of the monitoring windfallen area on the Babia Góra mountain. J. Ecol. Eng. 18, 193–199. <https://doi.org/10.12911/22998993/67097>
- [16] Zhang, W., Qi, J., Wan, P., Wang, H., Xie, D., Wang, X., Yan, G., 2016. An Easy-to-Use Airborne LiDAR Data Filtering Method Based on Cloth Simulation. Remote Sensing 8, 501. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs8060501>